

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Hironobu Sakaguchi (II)

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Hironobu Sakaguchi, as we saw in our previous article on the Japanese creative, is more than simply a professional. He is a visionary figure, capable of surrounding himself with other talented individuals who grew as programmers and artists alongside him. The video game industry as a whole has benefited from this, as have we as users and enthusiasts. Throughout this article, we will examine further major achievements in his career.

***Final Fantasy VII*: Square's breakthrough**

Following the unparalleled *Final Fantasy VI* and the various projects in which he was involved during the 1990s—covered in the previous article—Sakaguchi embarked on what would become a true odyssey to bring the next instalment to market.

Initially, *Final Fantasy VII* was planned for release on the Super Nintendo Entertainment System (Super Famicom), and later on the Nintendo 64, which at the time was still in development as Nintendo's next major console following the emergence of the PlayStation in 1994. However, a series of events between Nintendo and Sony—related to the potential adoption of optical media such as CDs—led Square to restart the project. A technical demo even showcased something akin to a remake or continuation of *Final Fantasy VI*, adapted to a three-dimensional polygonal environment.

As a result, the project that ultimately reached audiences became *Final Fantasy VII* as we remember it today, having undergone a significant transformation for release on Sony’s console—although earlier ideas from Sakaguchi remained embedded in its conception and development. This game marked a turning point in the industry, and not by chance. Its impact was the result of several key factors, which will be explored below.

Although it was not the first title bearing the Final Fantasy name to be released in Europe—that distinction belongs to the spin-off *Final Fantasy Mystic Quest*, known in Europe as *Mystic Quest Legend*, which is in fact part of the Mana (Seiken Densetsu) series—it was the first “mainline” Final Fantasy title in which Sakaguchi was directly involved for European audiences, serving as both producer and originator of the game’s concept. Once again, he worked alongside his regular collaborators, including Nobuo Uematsu and Yoshitaka Amano.

On this occasion, however, Amano’s involvement was more limited due to his engagement in other major projects, such as the establishment of workshops around the world and exhibitions of his work. As a result, a young Tetsuya Nomura took the lead in designing the characters as they appear in the game. Amano contributed more broadly to the visual world and other aspects of design, but with less direct input than in previous entries.

Over time, Nomura would gain increasing prominence within the Final Fantasy franchise and Square (later Square Enix). He also played a leading role in the remake of *Final Fantasy VII*, whose first instalment was released in 2020, with subsequent parts continuing the story, including *Rebirth*, released in 2024.

The protagonist of *Final Fantasy VII*, Cloud Strife, standing before the Shinra Tower. This is one of the game’s promotional images, on which several of its cover artworks were based.

Final Fantasy VII was one of Sony's major strategic releases after Nintendo missed the opportunity to publish the game on its upcoming Nintendo 64—fortunately, Nintendo enthusiasts can now enjoy it on the Nintendo Switch.

Initially, *Final Fantasy VII* was conceived by Hironobu Sakaguchi as a detective story set in New York in 1999. However, following the technical demo of a possible remake or sequel to *Final Fantasy VI* for the Nintendo 64, and the disagreements that arose between Squaresoft and Nintendo at the time, the project was completely reworked and ultimately released on Sony's PlayStation, with the story, setting, and characters we know today: the world of Gaia, cities such as Midgar, and the activist group Avalanche opposing Shinra and the formidable Sephiroth.

For this project, the team aimed to fully exploit the capabilities of Sony's new console, which featured a CD-ROM drive and the ability to render polygonal graphics without the need for additional hardware. As previously noted, Sakaguchi did not serve as director on this title, but as producer—indeed, he has not directed a *Final Fantasy* title since.

This instalment adopted a more contemporary aesthetic, moving away from the medieval-inspired settings of earlier entries. Its narrative explores the destructive impact of human activity on the planet, particularly through the exploitation of mako energy and the materia derived from it.

It follows the journey of former Soldier Cloud Strife and his companions in their struggle against the rogue Sephiroth, a fallen hero of Shinra, the vast corporation that functions as the central antagonist of the story. The game features numerous plot twists and deeply developed characters—such as Cloud himself—capable of both moving and entertaining players.

Although its graphics have aged poorly—unlike its design—the game's character development, narrative, and artistic direction left a profound impact on its audience. To enhance its storytelling, the game incorporated animated sequences (FMVs, or Full Motion Video), which would later become a hallmark of the *Final Fantasy* series.

The use of optical discs, with significantly greater storage capacity than the cartridges used by other consoles at the time, allowed for high-quality computer-generated cinematic sequences in key moments of the game. These sequences reflected a production approach similar to that of animation studios, which allocate greater resources to the most narratively significant scenes.

Final Fantasy VII was also the first video game to be developed in a manner comparable to major film productions—what would later be termed “AAA video games”. It involved a development team of over 120 artists and programmers and an exceptionally large budget for the 1990s: approximately \$145 million, of which \$100 million were allocated to marketing and advertising.

The game was a global success and has since generated numerous spin-offs, sequels, and, as mentioned earlier, a remake. Sakaguchi's team continued to release major entries in the franchise, including *Final Fantasy VIII* (1999) and *Final Fantasy IX* (2000), both of which were also released in Western markets, where the series had by then become firmly established.

Final Fantasy X marked the franchise's transition to the sixth generation of consoles, launching on the PlayStation 2 in 2001. By this point, Sakaguchi was less directly involved, and Yoshinori Kitase assumed the role of director. A trusted collaborator, Kitase helped ensure that this instalment would be regarded as one of the finest in the series.

Featuring unforgettable characters such as Auron and Yuna, and a deeply emotional narrative, *Final Fantasy X* also represented a major technical achievement. It offered fully 3D graphics—aside from some pre-rendered environments, continuing a trend that began with *Final Fantasy VII*—as well as voice acting and the series' characteristic cinematic sequences.

The soundtrack was composed collaboratively by Nobuo Uematsu, Masashi Hamauzu, and Junya Nakano, and includes some of the most celebrated pieces in the franchise.

Beyond *Final Fantasy*

Sakaguchi gradually distanced himself from the series, which is understandable given his growing interest in other projects. Among these was his ambition to become a film director, realised in 2001 with *Final Fantasy: The Spirits Within*—ironically, despite its title, quite unlike the traditional Final Fantasy video game experience. It was the first feature-length film to pursue a photorealistic aesthetic using fully computer-generated imagery.

Although the film received poor reviews and resulted in significant financial losses, this did not deter Sakaguchi, who continued to pursue new creative ventures beyond the franchise that had made him famous.

In 2003, Square merged with Enix, partly as a consequence of the financial losses incurred by the film. This merger resulted in the formation of Square Enix, now responsible for the franchises of both former rivals, including Final Fantasy and Dragon Quest.

Sakaguchi's departure from Square was widely noted, and there were concerns that the Final Fantasy franchise might decline without him. However, Square—and later Square Enix—continued to release notable titles such as *Final Fantasy XI*, *XII*, and the *Final Fantasy VII* remake project (2020–2024), which brought players back to Midgar during the global pandemic.

Sakaguchi went on to found Mistwalker in 2004. Microsoft was the first company to approach him—rather than Sony—supporting the creation of the studio during the era of the successful Xbox 360. Through this collaboration, Sakaguchi released two notable RPGs for the platform: *Blue Dragon* (2006) and *Lost Odyssey* (2007), both of which draw heavily on the traditions of the RPG “Golden Age”.

For these titles, Sakaguchi collaborated with renowned manga artists Akira Toriyama and Takehiko Inoue, respectively. Nevertheless, he did not align himself exclusively with a single company, instead pursuing a flexible approach that led to projects such as *ASH: Archaic Sealed Heat* (2007) for Nintendo DS and *The Last Story* (2011) for Wii.

On the left, artwork by Akira Toriyama for *Blue Dragon*, and on the right, artwork by Takehiko Inoue applied to *Lost Odyssey*.

Closely associated with the RPG genre, Hironobu Sakaguchi has also participated in a variety of other projects, such as the fighting game series *Bushido Blade*. Nevertheless, he occasionally returns to his roots, as in *Terra Battle* (2014), which combined simple yet engaging and innovative ideas, blending RPG mechanics with card-based systems, tactical role-playing elements, and puzzle gameplay. The game was released for Android and iOS devices.

Despite its success on mobile platforms—its servers remained active until 2020—its sequel and the spin-off *Terra Wars* did not achieve the same level of success and ultimately failed to gain traction.

Hironobu Sakaguchi today

What has Sakaguchi been working on most recently? The answer is the acclaimed *Fantasian*, released in 2021 for various Apple devices. The project originated in 2018, when Sakaguchi revisited *Final Fantasy VI* alongside members of the original development team. This experience inspired him to create a new title that would return to the design philosophy of his earlier works.

After decades of working independently, Sakaguchi reconnected with Square Enix, which supported the release of *Fantasian* on platforms beyond iOS. The game is now available on Nintendo Switch, PlayStation 4, PlayStation 5, PC, and Xbox Series X and Series S.

The game represents a clear return to the classic RPGs of previous decades, combining traditional Japanese role-playing mechanics—such as turn-based combat triggered by random encounters—with a unique world constructed using handcrafted dioramas, created with the assistance of artists such as Akira Toriyama. Nobuo Uematsu also contributed to the soundtrack, further enhancing the nostalgic qualities of the title.

Fantasian integrates real-world elements into its game environments through the use of camera-equipped drones, which scan physical objects and transform them into three-dimensional assets within the game. The second part of the title was released on Apple Arcade, and in 2024 both parts were finally made available beyond Apple platforms in a package titled *Neo Dimension*. For players with access to compatible platforms, *Fantasian* is highly recommended, as it successfully evokes the spirit of Sakaguchi's earlier works and offers a compelling return to the foundations of the genre.

Screenshot from *Fantasian Neo Dimension*, which includes both parts of *Fantasian*. The image highlights the blend of computer-generated graphics and real-world diorama environments.

Following *Fantasian*, Hironobu Sakaguchi considered taking a break and possibly retiring, as he felt that, due to his age—and having become a grandfather—he might no longer have the same level of energy required to develop video games as he had throughout his earlier career.

To conclude, we invite readers to follow the link provided to watch a behind-the-scenes video offering insight into the development of *Fantasian*, showcasing how Sakaguchi's team constructed elements of the game, accompanied by music composed by Nobuo Uematsu. The video is featured on Sakaguchi's official YouTube channel.

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Domenech Alcaide, Andrés (2017), *Los videojuegos como producto del arte: La influencia e importancia del dibujo, del cómic y otras artes en su historia* (Doctoral thesis), University of Granada, Granada; Forbes; Square-Enix official website | **Text by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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